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CO₂-Water Alternating Gas Injection performance prediction by employing Machine Learning Techniques

Shahab Ud Din*, Xue Liang*, Fulong Ning**, Dongdong Guo***

* College of Petroleum Engineering, China University of Petroleum, Beijing, 102249, China

** Faculty of Engineering, China University of Geosciences (Wuhan), 430074, China

*** School of Earth and Environment, Anhui University of Science and Technology, Huainan, 232001, China.

Correspondence Email: enr.shahab.pg@gmail.com

CO₂ injection is an effective technique for enhanced oil recovery (EOR), especially in depleted oil fields, and can be employed as both secondary and tertiary recovery methods. The key benefits of CO₂ injection are that it not only enhances oil recovery but can also sequester CO₂, which helps in reducing CO₂ emissions. CO₂ Water Alternating Gas (CO₂-WAG) is a type of CO₂-EOR that circumvents issues like fingering and early breakthroughs in CO₂ injections. However, the performance of CO₂-WAG tied to the injection parameters makes the numerical simulations computationally intensive. This study utilised Machine Learning (ML) techniques to predict CO₂-WAG performance under various injection scenarios. CMG simulation software was utilized to devise 2400 simulation models that represent diverse CO₂ -WAG scenarios, where 80 % of the data was used for training and 20 % was utilised for testing the model. A hybrid model is employed to predict the performance indicators of CO₂-WAG, such as cumulative oil production, sequestration amount, and efficiency. Where injection rates (water and CO₂), cycle size, and cycle lengths were considered as the four input parameters. The employed hybrid model outperforms traditional algorithms individually. The results show congruence between the actual and predicted values. The R² values are 0.99, 0.97, and 0.99 for oil, CO₂ sequestration and efficiency, respectively. Whereas the average deviation factor is oil, CO₂ sequestration and efficiency are 2.1%, 2.3%, and 2.4%, respectively. Furthermore, the ML technique shows computational efficiency; it only takes 15 seconds for predictions, whereas CMG simulation requires more than 2 days for simulation runs. The above results indicate that the proposed method is robust and accurately predicts CO₂-WAG performance. The results of the study provide valuable insights for optimization and will also help the engineers to perform sensitivity analysis robustly.